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(ZONE D)**

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EDITORIAL

We are delighted to present to our esteemed readers The Maiden Edition of THE SCALE: Volume 1, Number 1, (December 2021) our inter-disciplinary journal. The journal which is a bi-annual publication of the Academic Staff Union of Polytechnics, (ASUP) Zone D, is envisioned to publish scholarly and professional articles and reports which meet acceptable class of global academic best practice. As an inter-disciplinary journal, it is committed to the provision of an academic platform for scholars and practitioners in all disciplines to ventilate intellectual view points and research findings on contemporary global issues.

In this edition, we serve you with seventy five (75) incisive and educative articles diligently peer-reviewed by our team of erudite scholars from Polytechnics and Universities. Many of the articles here are actually products of the 5th bi- annual ASUP ZONE D Conference held in March 2021 at Federal Polytechnic, Nekede-Owerri, Imo State, Nigeria.

UDOCHUKWU PRECIOUS NWAKODO

Editor-in-chief

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ARTICLES AND CONTRIBUTORS

TECHNOLOGICAL INNOVATION FOR SUSTAINABLE ECONOMIC AND SOCIAL DEVELOPMENT IN A POST-COVID-19 NIGERIA

By PROF. F. EZIONYE EBOH Page 01
A Lead Paper Presented at the 5th Academic Staff Union of Polytechnics (ASUP), Zone D National Conference 3rd-5th March, 2021, ASUP Complex, Federal Polytechnic, Nekede Owerri, Imo State

A CRITICAL EVALUATION OF INDUSTRIALIZATION STRATEGIES AND POLICIES IN NIGERIA (FROM 2002--2016)

OGURU, Ayibamiebi Foster & EKADI, Ebikewen Imo Hannah Page 11

A PRAGMATIC STUDY OF THE LANGUAGE OF SPORTS IN SELECTED SPORTS DOCUMENTS

OKAFOR, Theodore Mad; OGAYI, Martin C. (Ph.D) & EKECHI, Christian page 16

AN OPTIMIZED CLASSIFICATION OF BREAST CANCER: USING TREE-BASED PIPELINE OPTIMIZATION TOOL

A. A. ODUMOSU; Q. A. ALATISHE & A. A. ADEDEJI Page 26

ANALYSIS OF THE GOAL OF ETHICS EDUCATION AMONG ACCOUNTANCY STAFF AND STUDENTS OF FEDERAL POLYTECHNIC BIDA, NIGER STATE

SOLANKE, Abiola Abosedo Page 32

ANALYTICAL COMPARISON BETWEEN FIRST AND SECOND WAVES OF COVID-19 INFECTION RATE IN NIGERIA

MANSI Walamam Egbo Page 40

ASSESSMENT OF POLYTYPIC AROMATIC HYDROCARBON (PAH) DISTRIBUTION IN DRY SEASON OF AMBIENT AIR OF OIL PRODUCING COMMUNITIES OF EGBEMA, IMO STATE, NIGERIA.

G.C. ANYANWU (Ph.D) & E. O. OHAERI Page 53

COVID-19 CRISIS AND ITS EFFECT ON SURVIVAL STRATEGIES OF SMALL-SCALE BUSINESS ENTERPRISES

BROGHOMA, Lawal. M & OGHOGHO, Roseline O. Page 60

COVID-19 PANDEMIC AND THE SOCIO- ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT OF NIGERIA: AN ASSESSMENT OF GOVERNMENT INTERVENTIONS

IWEZU Joseph Iwezu; AGBOGWE Cynthia & ANIEMEKE Frederick Page 68

DESIGN AND DEVELOPMENT OF INTEGER LINEAR PROGRAMMING SOFTWARE USING VISUAL BASIC PROGRAMMING LANGUAGE

C.O. AMGBARI; T.O. SUOWARE & A. KABIAMOWEI Page 78

DETERMINATION OF SOME HEAVY AND PRECIOUS METALS FROM PRINTED CIRCUIT BOARD (PCB) FROM A TELEVISION SET BY ATOMIC ABSORPTION SPECTROPHOMETER

GBARAKORO, S. L. & KONNE, J. L. Page 82

DETERMINATION OF THE PHYSICAL AND MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF NEGRO PEPPER UDA SEED (XYLOPIA AETHIOPICA)

AGU, Romanus S., OMEJE, Cornelius, OKORO, Alex C, AGU, Valentine O., IGWILO, Ibezim J. Page 86

DEVELOPMENT OF A WELDING FUME EXTRACTOR.

UKWUOMA, Ugochukwu Francis, EHIRIM, Victor Page 96

EDUCATION AND TECHNOLOGICAL DEVELOPMENT IN NIGERIA: EMERGING ISSUES FROM COVID-19

OBISIKE, Iheanyi Osondu (Ph.D) & IDEOZU, Mark U. Page 101

EFFECT OF INDIRECT TAXATION ON ECONOMIC GROWTH IN NIGERIA

ONYEWUCHI, Veronica Eyuuche (Ph.D) Page 107

EFFECT OF PROCESS VARIABLES ON PHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF EXTRUDED SNACKS PRODUCED FROM BLENDS OF SORGHUM, AFRICAN YAM BEAN AND MORINGA LEAF POWDER

NWAKALOR, Chizoba Nkiru Page 119

EFFECT OF SOIL SAMPLING DEPTH ON HEAVY METAL CONCENTRATION AND SOME PHYSIOCHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF SOIL AT TWO AUTOMOBILE MECHANIC VILLAGES IN OWERRI, IMO STATE
OKORO, A.C., AGU, R.S., NWACHUKWU, C.P., UGWU, E.I. & NZEKWE, C.A
 Page 127

EFFECT OF TECHNOLOGICAL INNOVATION ON FEDERAL TAX REVENUE, IMPLICATION FOR POST COVID-19 REVENUE MOBILIZATION: FROM VALUE ADDED TAX PERSPECTIVE
OKORO, T. C. & OBI B. C. (Ph.D)
 Page 139

ELEMENTAL CONCENTRATION OF SOME NIGERIAN COAL SAMPLES BY INSTRUMENTAL NEUTRON ACTIVATION ANALYSIS
OMEJE, Cornelius U ;AGU, Romanus S; OKORO, Alex C; AGU, Valentine O & IGWILO, Ibezim J.
 Page 148

EMERGING TECHNOLOGIES IN EFFECTIVE LIBRARY SERVICES: OPEN-SOURCE TECHNOLOGIES AND LIBRARY SOFTWARE
KALU, Chidi; Onuoha (CLN); NWORIE ; Josiah Chukwuma Ph.D (CLN) & SABA, Fatima Muhammad (CLN)
 Page 153

EMPLOYEE PARTICIPATION IN DECISION MAKING AND ACHIEVEMENT OF ORGANIZATIONAL GOALS: A STUDY OF ABIA STATE COLLEGE OF HEALTH SCIENCES AND MANAGEMENT TECHNOLOGY ABA ,2018-2019.
UBANI, Goodluck Eguzoikpe; & NWAKODO, Udochukwu, Precious
 Page 161

ENHANCING PRODUCTIVITY IN AN ORGANIZATION THROUGH PERSONNEL TRAINING AND DEVELOPMENT: A CASE STUDY OF MTN NIGERIA, PLC. PORT HARCOURT BRANCH
GIDEON, Mudiem Titus.
 Page 153

ENVIRONMENT AND IMPLEMENTATION OF LEGAL REQUIREMENTS IN CAPITAL PROJECTS
QS ONYEKWENA, Tobechukwu
 Page 184

EVALUATION OF BACTERIOLOGICAL QUALITY OF SOYBEAN MILK BEVERAGE SOLD IN EKWULOBIA AND OKO METROPOLIS
NDIFE, Rachael Chinaza & CHUKWUMBAH, Emmanuel Chukwuemeka .
 Page 191

EVALUATION OF DIFFERENT CONCRETE MIX USING PARTICULATE PALM KERNEL SHELL
Engr. AZIEGBEMHIN, Ehiabhi Paul
 Page 198

EXAMINING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF BLENDED LEARNING AS A NEW NORMAL FOR SCHOOLS SURVIVAL IN POST-COVID-19 NIGERIA
ANHO, Erere Joy (Ph.D)
 Page 206

FARMERS-HERDERS CRISES AND FOOD INFLATION IN NIGERIA: EVIDENCE FROM DELTA STATE
OGANA Michael; MORDI Kenneth Ejime; & OGALA Sunday Christian
 Page 213

FEASIBILITY STUDY OF ANDROID APPLICATION IN NBTE- ACCREDITED CURRICULUM OF ARCHITECTURAL TECHNOLOGY EDUCATION
ONWUKWE, Chukwuemeka S.O; ONYEKWENA, Tobechukwu & OGBUOKIRI, Obinna A.C.
 Page 223

FIRE PROTECTION AND SAFETY ON BUILDING SITE
Qs ONYEKWENA, Tobechukwu _ & ONWUKWE, Chukwuemeka Ozioma Stanislaus
 Page 234

I.C.T AND EDUCATION MANAGEMENT IN PANDEMIC SITUATIONS IN NIGERIA: PROBLEMS AND PROSPECTS.
IMUETINYAN, Sophia Osayomwanbor
 Page 241

IMPACT OF MULTIMEDIA CONTENTS IN BROADCASTING
OHWO, Stephen O. & ERIRHI, Jonathan O. (Ph.D)
 Page 250

IMPERATIVES OF E-GOVERNANCE AND PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION IN NIGERIA
OKAFOR, Okafor Ogbonnaya & NWAKODO, Udochukwu Precious
 Page 263

FEASIBILITY STUDY OF ANDROID APPLICATION IN NBTE-ACCREDITED CURRICULUM OF ARCHITECTURAL TECHNOLOGY EDUCATION

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Abstract

The recently reviewed curricula for Architectural Technology Education by the NBTE released as at October, 2020 is still recommending Windows XP and Windows Vista operating systems and applications as learning resources for all courses at both the HND and ND levels of Architectural Technology. These operating systems are more than a decade old, rigid and obsolete. To this end, this study is premised on investigating the practicability of adopting android operating systems and their applications as learning resources in teaching and learning course modules in Architectural Technology Education. Cross-sectional survey research methodology was adopted to elicit responses from participants sampled from NBTE-accredited polytechnics domiciled in the six geopolitical regions of the country. Slovin's formula ($n = N / (1 + Ne^2)$) as shown in section 2.1.2 employing confidence level of 95% with an alpha level of 0.05 was used to generate sample size for each polytechnic. Respondents were composed of technologists/instructors, lecturers and HND/ND incoming students. A total of six (6) polytechnics, one from each geopolitical zone, and three hundred and fifty-three (353) respondents provided data for this study. Data collated and analyzed provided results which indicated that android operating systems and their widgets provided visualized, user-friendly, affordable and interactive capabilities for architecture students and teachers. This will ensure overall above par performance of students in General Studies/Education, Foundation and Professional Courses thus providing a high-tech driven crop of middle manpower in Architectural Technology.

Keywords: Alpha level, Android, Architectural Technology, Operating System, Widgets.

INTRODUCTION

Android is one of the most useful and powerful operating systems because of its supporting feature. In several aspects, smartphones are considered as important tools of innovation. Android technology is also a remarkable tool for distributing new knowledge and proffering viable solutions. Due to technological inventions, the android operating system has undergone great changes and it is running on countless models of smartphones, personal computers, tablets, as well as many other devices (Odeh & Nwampkpa 2018). With the availability of smartphone devices and advancement in mobile technology, developers are designing interactive and effective android applications which can be used for learning and teaching architecture through single platform Philip 2016. Careful investigation of the recently reviewed curricula of the NBTE for Architectural Technology shows new addition of courses both at the ND and HND level. The courses, including computer courses, have specified learning resources which only revolve around operating systems (OS) like Windows XP and Vista. It's even worrisome to note that both operating systems are no longer in use today as they have been replaced by far more intelligent and robust operating systems. While Windows XP was released in October 25, 2001 (Microsoft 2021) Windows Vista debuted in January 30, 2007 (Fisher 2021). Invariably, operating systems listed as learning resources in a 2020 document are more than a decade old. The curricula never listed android as a learning resource.

To this end, this study is aimed at finding out the practicability of adopting android applications in teaching and learning course modules domiciled in Architectural Technology Education in NBTE-accredited polytechnics. This is ensured by the following specific objectives:

a. To initiate an innovative pedagogy of Architectural Technology by incorporating

in the curricula learning resources and operating systems with improved interface design, interaction, visualization capabilities and system functionalities;

b. To groom a technically innovative crop of manpower that can transform their knowledge to actual practice through the use, efficiency, output index and visualization techniques of android applications;

c. To improve on the capacity of preferring architectural solutions of both students and instructors/technologists by providing affordable and cost-effective platforms powered by android operating systems and applications;

d. To build a new order of middle manpower that know their onions as concerns security of data, legal/copyright fireworks and privacy clauses;

e. To build an output-driven middle manpower based on operational parameters in order to promote problem-solving, encourage literacy development and creative thinking skills through android applications.

Android applications are gradually displacing traditional architectural design and learning technologies thus becoming more advanced in the education sector due to its innovative and efficient technologies like virtual Reality (VR) and Augmented Reality (AR). In Architectural education for visualization of three-dimensional (3D) model, students require this technology on mobile devices to compare their 3D models with real world objects. Image architecture, virtual scene and digital simulation, among other applications, are examples of digital technologies that have been involved in the education process of architectural education to replace traditional education tools which was mainly based on two dimensional (2D) sketches on physical 3D models. Integration of complete digital teaching like computer aided drafting (CAD), modeling and enumerating has

become the main subject in Architectural education. Over the past decades, mobile technologies are providing more effective educational methods for classrooms and outdoor learning. The rest of the paper is further structured as follows:

- i. Section I improves an overview of android;
- ii. Section II presents the basic components of android application;
- iii. Section III outlines the use of android application in the education sector;
- iv. Section IV describes Architectural Technology Education;
- v. Section V highlights the sample size calculations adopting the Slovin's Formula, collation and analysis of data gathered in the course of the study;
- vi. Section VI discusses the interpretation of results generated from the study;
- vii. Section VII put forward recommendations as informed by the study while
- viii. Section VIII offers final conclusive notes.

Note. From *Learning Android* (1st ed., p. 1-2), by Marko Gargenta, 2011, O'Reilly Media Inc., 1005, Gravenstein Highway North, Sebastopol, CA 95472.

Overview of Android

Android is a popular, comprehensive

open-source platform and Linux based operating system for mobile devices. Its operating system (OS) which was developed by the Open Handset Alliance (OHA), led by Google, was primarily designed for touch screen mobile devices such as tablet computers and smartphones. These days, android is one of the most sought-after and widely used mobile operating system because of its features such as interactive user interface (UI), connectivity, multi-touch, multitasking storage, media support, web browser, messaging, multi-language, GCM, resizable widgets, android beam and wi-fi direct. Android OS has been released in a number of versions. They include Android Astro (1.0), Bender (1.1), Cupcake (1.5), Donut (1.6), Eclair (2.0), Froyo (2.2.x), Gingerbread (2.3.x), Honeycomb (3.0), Ice Cream Sandwich (4.0.x), Jelly Bean (4.x), KitKat (4.4), Lollipop (5.0), Marshmallow (6.0), Nogut (7.0), Oreo (8.0), Pie (9) and Q (10) which is the latest released version of android (**J.R, 2021.**) Figure 1 shows the acceptability index of android and seven main reasons why android is so popular. Nowadays, a good number of architectural applications are available on android thus helping architectural students to work smarter instead of harder (**Ukoh & Nwamgbe 2019**)

Note. From *Android Application Development with Kotlin*, 57), by Hardik Trivedi, 2020, *BPB Publications* 245, Jurgen, Cincinnati USA.

Basic Components of Android Application

In recent years, wireless communication techniques and android devices have evolved significantly in daily life style of individuals. This has led to a high demand for developing and android applications that run on android devices. This section outlines necessary basic components of an android application as can be seen in figure 2. The figure shows essential building blocks of an android application. Activity is a class that is considered as an entry point for users that represents a single screen. A messenger application might have an activity that shows a new notification, another activity which reads messages and another which composes a new message.

Each activity is independent of one another. **For example**, camera application can be started in an email application to compose an email that shares an image. Broadcast Receiver is a component that responds to broadcast messages from another application or the same system. It can also deliver broadcasts to applications that are not running. **A good example is when users get "battery-low" notifications.** Android developers can use broadcast messages in the application or outside the normal flow. Service is a component that runs in the background while acting as an invisible worker in the application. It keeps updating data sources and activities. It also **broadcasts intents** and performs tasks when applications are not active. An example of service is when we can surf the internet or use any other application while listening to music. Content Provider is a component that allows applications to share data among multiple applications. It hides the details of the database and can be used to read and write private data of the application which is not shared. Widgets are variations of Broadcast Receivers and essential aspects of **home screen customization.** They display data and allow users to perform actions on

them. There are various types of widgets as refers:

- i. **Information widget:** These widgets display crucial information and track how the information changes over time.
- ii. **Collection widget:** As the name depicts, collection widgets are a collection of information of the same type. Its use is for browsing information and opening any one of the elements to view details.
- iii. **Control widget:** These widgets display functionalities and by using them, the user can trigger from home screen without opening the application.
- iv. **Hybrid widget:** These widgets combine features of all the other three widgets. Example – music player widget is a control widget but it also informs the user about which track is playing currently, which means it is a combination of control and information thus it is termed as hybrid widget.

Notifications alert users when the application is not visible or is inactive. This alert flashes on the screen and then disappears. An example is notification of new incoming message which briefly pops up on the screen for few seconds **Simon 2021.**

Note. From *Android Application Development for the Intel Platform* by Ryan Cohen and Tao Wang, 2014, Apress Open, Intel Software College, Shanghai, China.

Android Application in Education Sector:

In the education sector, the rapid evolution and advancement of wireless portable technology, such as mobile devices, has led to radical development. A wide variety of android applications are available these days for learning and teaching. Applications are designed these days to be effective, engaging and interactive. Over the last few years, mobile learning has brought tremendous success with the possibility of learning anywhere, anytime by using android-based learning application (**Handoyono & Rabiman, 2020**). Nowadays, android apps are more convenient and user-friendly for students while bringing different approaches in educational instructions such as 'knowledge objects' and 'learning objects. Android applications have enriched and enhanced the current educational system to provide permanent, effective and productive learning outcomes in academic institutions (**Ryan & Tao, 2014**). In the education sector, interactive android applications motivate learners, educators and instructors to adopt mobile learning as teaching and learning tools (**Luis Francisco Mendes Gabriel Pedro, 2018**). Educational android applications provide various benefits of learning in education sector such as flexible, self-regulated, interactive, collaborative and experimental learning. Android applications have increased students learning experience and become meaningful, systematic, organized and socially interactive (**Adesti, 2019**) as shown in figure 3.

Android applications facilitate various feasible educational benefits for learners and educators such as sharing information, exchanging information and ideas with associates through digital method, discuss information with groups through centralized system, organize and select correct information, scan or capture needed information, access dictionary, check spelling and translate text from one

language to another language and vice versa. Others include social interaction technologies for students and instructors (i.e., WhatsApp, Blog, Facebook, Twitter, Email), multiple representation of information such as audio and video session for participants, share findings and discussion. These benefits allow users to quickly and broadly get knowledge in digital manner, facilitate game-based learning and encourage 3D learning method with multiple interaction forms (**Rahman 2000**).

Architectural Technology Education

Architecture is an amalgam of science and art and it is also considered as social engineering and practical art. Technology [refers](#) to methods, systems, and devices which are the result of [scientific](#) knowledge being used for practical [purposes](#). Education means transfer of systematic and necessary information directly or indirectly from one generation to other generation with proper teaching techniques for more informed learning outcomes. It is categorized into sub-sections such as educational environment, educational tools, educational techniques and educational psychology. Architectural Technology Education can then be said to be the educational plan laid out to groom scholars both in the academic and professional genre of the architectural discipline through the deployment of technology (**Malecha, 2017**).

Architectural Technology Education (ATE) is guided by curricula which maintains the combination of professional training and academic scholarship. This includes not just knowledge of drafting, constructional elements, sketching, building materials, but also includes history, geometry, philosophy/sociology, etc. There are two types of educational techniques in architectural technology education. They are traditional techniques (i.e., problem-solving, question and answer, pair and group works,

discussion, case study, narrating lectures, etc.) and digital techniques (i.e., e-learning, Virtual Reality (VR), Artificial Intelligence (AI), 3D-modelling, etc.). Architecture is a completely developed discipline and it consists mainly of collaborative and synthetic profession (**The University of Nottingham 2020**). In ATE programme, students have to learn architectural theory and history, problem-solving, building design on computer aided design and drafting, analyzing and communication, structures, physical science, building construction methods and professional practice (National Board for Technical Education 2020).

ATE is based on teacher-oriented and student-oriented programmes in which theoretical lectures are managed in teacher-oriented manner and design studio, which is managed in both teacher and student-oriented manners. In ATE, it is necessary for students to be involved in building construction, modeling, planning and designing. It is expected that architectural students should have creative aptitude, software skills and technical knowledge to become a professional architect (**Architects Registration Council of Nigeria 2020**).

Sample Size, Collation and Analysis of Data

Cross-sectional survey research methodology was adopted to elicit responses from participating institutions and respondents sampled from NBTE-accredited polytechnics domiciled in the six geopolitical regions of the country. These surveys elicited responses from alpha variables which are coalesced from the primary objectives. Data was sourced from six (6) NBTE-accredited polytechnics across the country, one from each geopolitical zone. For the purposes of integrity and unbiased reportage, this study intentionally avoided adopting data from the researchers' domiciled institution. They include:

i. Akanu Ibiam Federal Polytechnic Unwana - representing the south-east geopolitical

zone;

ii. Akwa Ibom State Polytechnic, Ikot Osurua, Ikot Ekpene, Akwa Ibom State- representing the south-south geopolitical zone;

iii. The Federal Polytechnic, Ado-Ekiti – representing the south-west geopolitical zone;

iv. The Benue State Polytechnic, Ugbokolo – representing the north-central geopolitical zone;

v. Hussaini Adamu Federal Polytechnic, Kazaure – representing the north-east geopolitical zone and

vi. Jigawa State Polytechnic, Dutse – representing the north-west geopolitical zone.

It is pertinent to note that The Benue State Polytechnic, Ugbokolo, Hussaini Adamu Federal Polytechnic, Kazaure and Jigawa State Polytechnic, Dutse had significant low population size due to the fact that their programmes in Architectural Technology terminates at the National Diploma level. Population size is made up of teachers (instructors, technologists and lecturers) and incoming ND I and HND I students only as these crop of students have higher contact hours to both academic staff and course modules. At the HND level, total contact hours at HND I level is 58 while contact hours at HND II level stands at 51 (**National Board for Technical Education, 2020**) At the ND level, total contact hours at ND I level is 56 while contact hours at the ND II levels stands at 53 (**National Board for Technical Education, 2020**) It must be noted also that all NBTE-accredited polytechnics must not exceed the statutory carrying capacity of intake in any academic session. However, polytechnics may have two streams of a particular class if and only if such polytechnics have the infrastructure and staff to support and carry the spill-over

intakes (Ekwerike 2018) .Population size and computation of sample size is as shown in table 2 while interpretation adopted is as shown in table 1 below:

Table Interpretation of ratings

S/n	Rating range	Interpretation
1	1 – 3	Completely unfeasible
2	4 – 5	Undecided; identification of research gap
3	6 – 10	Feasible; adoption advised

Note. Source from researchers' fieldwork conducted on the 28th May, 2021

Table Sample size

Generation of Sample Size						
Parameters of the Slovin's Formula	Institution 1: Akanu Ibiam Federal Polytechnic Unwana (academic staff + incoming students)	Institution 2: Akwa Ibom State Polytechnic, Ikot Osurua (academic staff + incoming students)	Institution 3: The Federal Polytechnic, Ado-Ekiti (academic staff + terminal students)	Institution 4: The Benue State Polytechnic (academic staff + incoming students)	Institution 5: Hussaini Adamu Federal Polytechnic, Kazaure (academic staff + incoming students)	Institution 6: Jigawa State Polytechnic, Duse (academic staff + incoming students)
Population size	81	97	101	47	48	45
Confidence Level	95%	95%	95%	95%	95%	95%
Margin of Error	5%	5%	5%	5%	5%	5%
Respondents/Sample size deducted from Slovin's formula ($n = N / (1 + Ne^2)$)	$\frac{81}{1 + 0.05^2 \times 81} = 68$	$\frac{97}{1 + 0.05^2 \times 97} = 78$	$\frac{101}{1 + 0.05^2 \times 101} = 81$	$\frac{47}{1 + 0.05^2 \times 47} = 42$	$\frac{48}{1 + 0.05^2 \times 48} = 43$	$\frac{45}{1 + 0.05^2 \times 45} = 41$

Note. Source from researchers' fieldwork conducted on the 28th May, 2021

The study was designed around a pent a grammatic perspective which allowed respondents to make objective assertions

based on inquiries surrounding each alpha. The pentagram, in this study, are five alpha variables that enabled the apt analysis of the

feasibility study. These alphas are derived to specifically address the objectives of this study. They include:

1. Technology & System Feasibility – responses surrounding the interfacedesign, interaction capabilities, visualization capabilities, user-friendliness and system functionalities of android applications are elicited from participants and appropriately rated.
2. Human-Factor/Time Feasibility - responses surrounding ease of use, efficiency, and output index of android applications are elicited from participants and appropriately rated.
3. Financial Feasibility – responses surrounding cost, maintenance and overall solution cost of android applications are elicited from participants and appropriately rated.
4. Legal Feasibility – responses surrounding privacy of data, security and legal concerns of android applications are elicited from participants and appropriately rated.

5.Operational/Resource Feasibility – responses surrounding how android applications solve problems and satisfies the requirement of users by using some operational parameter such as reliability, dis possibility, maintainability, sustain ability, support ability and producibility are elicited from participants and appropriately rated. Table 2 shows responses of participants and their ratings. Ratings adopted for this survey employed the descriptive rating scale as each answer option under each alpha variable is elaborately explained for the respondents. Each participant responds to four (4) questions under each alpha. The average response for each alpha is calculated. Invariably each participant is expected to have five (5) average responses from five (5) alpha variables. This is repeated for total number of respondents in each institution. The final feasibility rating of each alpha from each institution is deduced from the average of all respondents of a particular alpha.

Table Cumulative Rating Scores from participating institutions and final feasibility rating of Android Applications

Alpha Variables	Rating score average from 68 respondents of Institution 1	Rating score average from 78 respondents of Institution 2	Rating score average from 81 respondents of Institution 3	Rating score average from 42 respondents of Institution 4	Rating score average from 43 respondents of Institution 5	Rating score average from 41 respondents of Institution 6	Final Feasibility Rating (FFR) of Android Applications
	1 Technology & System Feasibility	7.8	7.5	8.2	8.1	7.9	
2 Human-Factor/Time Feasibility	8.2	8.3	8.3	8.1	7.9	8.4	8.2
3 Financial Feasibility	6.3	6.1	5.9	7.1	6.8	6.6	6.466667
4 Legal Feasibility	5.2	4.8	4.2	4.3	4.6	5.1	4.7
5 Operational/Resource Feasibility	7.6	7.5	7.9	6.9	8.1	7.7	7.616667

Note. Source from researchers' fieldwork conducted on the 1st June, 2021

INTERPRETATION OF RESULTS

This section proffers the interpretation of results deduced from of this study:

1. Technology & System capabilities: With an FFR of 7.9, the feasibility of adopting android operating system and applications in teaching and learning Architectural Technology course modules in NBTE-accredited polytechnics is assured.

2. Human-Factor/Time Feasibility: With an FFR of 8.2, the feasibility of adopting android operating system and applications in teaching and learning Architectural Technology course modules in NBTE-accredited polytechnics is assured.

3. Financial Feasibility: With an FFR of 6.5, the feasibility of adopting android operating system and applications in teaching and learning Architectural Technology course modules in NBTE-accredited polytechnics is assured.

4. Legal Feasibility: With an FFR of 4.7, the feasibility of adopting android operating system and applications in teaching and learning Architectural Technology course modules in NBTE-accredited polytechnics needs to be revisited and reviewed. Response from participants clearly showed a research gap.

5. Operational/Resource Feasibility: With an FFR of 7.6, the feasibility of adopting android operating system and applications in teaching and learning Architectural Technology course modules in NBTE-accredited polytechnics is assured.

CONCLUSION

This study mainly focuses on feasibility of android application-based learning and teaching method as compared to traditional method in education sector in architectural Technology Education. This study clearly shows that adoption of

android in the general pedagogy of Architectural Technology is practicable and feasible, though with some slight concerns. These bother on legal issues which can be resolved through enlightenment campaigns as they may even bother on sheer 'Ignorantia juris'. We simply cannot make any headway if, till now, our curricula are still guided by obsolete learning resources. The age of Covid-19, and AI is here and efforts must be made to be in sync with the demands of such times as failure to do so will definitely affect the quality of technologically-based middle manpower we produce in the Built Environment.

RECOMMENDATIONS

This study has identified some recommendations which must be addressed by the NBTE with respect to adopting and incorporating android operating system and its applications in teaching and learning course modules in Architectural Technology. This study recommends the adoption of android operating system for improved output especially in both foundation courses and professional courses. The widgets make learning quite interactive and easy to operate by teachers. Large classes can also be handled efficiently as most students are equipped with affordable and cheap android devices. Assessments and evaluations are made less cumbersome while deficiency in course modules can be easily and quickly re-assessed. However, it is pertinent to note that legal feasibility of android applications must be fully explored and researched to make for an encompassing acceptance. This is necessary to bring to fruition the developmental, technological and sustainable strides being made by the Nigerian Government in these insecure times of the pandemic era.

REFERENCES

Adesti, S. N. (2019). Android-Based Mobile

Learning : Its Effect on Students' Learning Achievement. *International Conference on Progressive Education (ICOPE 2019)* (pp. 100-103). Indonesia: Atlantis Press.

Architects Registration Council of Nigeria. (2020, November 11). Becoming a professional architect. Abuja, Abuja, Nigeria.

Diadon. A. W. (2014). *Architectural Revolution*, Stuttgart: Kremlin.

Ekwerike. J. C. (2018). Compilation of Accreditation Reports of Polytechnics from 2012 - 2017. *International Journal of Education Issues and Development*, 334-346.

Fisher. T. (2021, July 29). Microsoft Windows Vista. Retrieved from Lifewire: <https://www.lifewire.com/windows-vista-2626311>

Greg. D. (2018). *Financial feasibility of android applications*. Washimton: Oak press.

Handoyono, N. A., & Rabiman. (2020). Development of android-based learning application in EFI materials for vocational schools. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 1-9.

Hardik . T. (2Q2Q). *Android Application Development with Kotlin*. Jurgen: Cincinnati, USA.

Harkiran, T. (2021, March 4). Top Programming Languages for Android App Development. Retrieved from *Geeks for Geeks*: <https://www.geeksforgeeks.org/top-programming-languages-for-android-app-development/#>text=While%20Java%20is%20the%20official,used%20for%20Android%20App%20Development>.

J.R. R. (2021, July 12). Android versions: A

living history from 1.0 to 12. Retrieved from *Computer World: The voice of business technology*: <https://www.computerworld.com/article/3235946/android-versions-a-living-history-from-1-0-to-today.html>

Luis Francisco Mendes Gabriel Pedro, C. M. (2018). A critical review of mobile learning integration in formal educational contexts. *International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education*, 23-28.

Malecha. M. J. (2017). *Architectural Education*. Athens: Athens Technological Organization.

Marko . G. (2011). *Learning Android*. California: O'Reilly Media, Inc.

Microsoft. (2017, November 12). *Modern Teaching and Learning*. Switzerland, Sweden.

Microsoft Wiki. (2021, July 12). Whistler 2000-2001. Retrieved from *Windows XP*: https://microsoft.fandom.com/wiki/Windows_XP

National Board for Technical Education. (2020, July 14). *Curriculum for ND and HND Architectural Education Technology*. Abuja, Abuja, Nigeria.

Odeh. A. F. & Nwamkpa, A. C. (2018). *Transforming Architectural Education. The Andriod Technology and Transformation in Education* (pp. 34-38). Enugu: The Architects Registration Council of Nigeria.

Olsen, F. S. (2015). *Computer-aided Design and Architecture*. Bath: Elsevier.

Philip. O. (2016). *Digitalizing instructions in*

- Architectural Education. Enugu: Cromwell Publishers.
- Rahman, A. (2000, November 1). Development of an Integrated Traditional and Scientific Knowledge Base: A Mechanism for Accessing, BenefitSharing and Documenting Traditional Knowledge for Sustainable Socio-Economic Development and Poverty Alleviation. UNCTAD Expert Meeting on Systems and National Experiences for Protecting Traditional Knowledge, Innovations and Practices, pp. 1-15.
- Ryan, C.. & Tao, W. (2014). Android Application Development for the Intel Platform. Shanghai: Apress Open.
- Simon. E. J. (2021, July 15). Android Application Components with Implementation & Examples. Retrieved from Data Flair: <https://data-flair.training/blogs/android-application-components/>
- The University of Nottingham. (2020, May 11). Architecture with Collaborative Practice. Nottingham, Nottingham, United Kingdom.
- Ukoh, A. D., & Nwamgbe, D. S. (2019). Android Architecture: The Smart Output. Los Angeles: Springfield.

FIRE PROTECTION AND SAFETY ON BUILDING SITE

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Abstract

The principal source of fire in buildings/building sites is their content. Obviously, the combustibility of the content of buildings varies considerably. This paper considers the effects of fire on the structure and finishes building sites, and highlights methods and equipment used for protecting the building and its occupants from the effect of fire. It also highlights measures that are necessary to ensure the safety of men and materials on a building site. The paper concludes that the purpose of fire protection is to ensure the protection of life, materials, goods and activities within a building or on a building internally and in relation to adjacent buildings internally and in relation to adjacent buildings, and satisfactory planning and construction of means of escape, and installation of protective service for firefighting in the building and the site. In addition, schedule 5 of Health and Safety at Work etc Act 1974 and the Building Regulations make it mandatory for any contractor or client on a building site to provide first aid boxes, shelter and accommodation for clothing and for taking meals on every site, protective clothing, fencing and provision of security guard etc to ensure their safety. That way will be able to achieve optimum fire protection in building sites.

Keywords: Fire, Protection, Safety, Building site.

INTRODUCTION

Fire protection is every measures for the prevention, detection and extinction of fire, as well as the reduction or prevention of fire damage or loss of life and the design of building to resist fire (i.e. structural protection) it also the protection of the occupants, contents and structure of building/site from the risks associated with fire. The subject is of vital importance and is so linked with the design and construction of building that is essential to understand the factors which influence the nature and form of the protection and of the principles which are the basis of the various building regulations covering fire protection of

building and sites.

Section I of part E of Building Regulation is concerned with structural fire precautions and Section II with means of escape, since the regulations are made in the interest of public health and safety, they do not attempt to achieve non-combustible buildings, but rather to ensure the safety of the building/sites, it occupants and the public. Building must therefore be constructed so that, in the event of fire;

a.They will resist collapse for a sufficient period of time to allow evacuation of the occupants and